

Correction to: Beyond the Annual and Aggregate Measurement of Household Inequality: The Case Study of Lake Naivasha Basin, Kenya

Maria Sassi¹ · Gopal Trital¹ · Poushali Bhattacharjee¹

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Correction to: The European Journal of Development Research <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-021-00380-6>

During the correction process some typos have been overlooked:

In the section Empirical Strategy, two lines below Eq. 4 *in the* is misspelled with *it*.

One line above Eq. 4a, *food expenditure* is printed as *fooxpenditure*.

One line above Eq. 4b, there is a missing space before *at*.

Three lines above Eq. 5, *we might* is printed as *wmight*.

Nine lines below Eq. 5, *Equation* is printed as *Eation*.

Five lines below Eq. 7, *unchanged* is printed as *unchang*.

One line below Eq. 9, *As explained* is printed as *Aexplained*.

Six lines below Eq. 9, *less* is printed as *ls*.

Eight lines below Eq. 9, *In our* is printed as *Iour*.

One line above Eq. 11, *earnings* is printed as *enings*.

Two lines below Eq. 11, *to the* is printed as *tthe*.

Six lines below Eq. 11, *In general* is printed as *Iral*.

The first sub-heading of Results and Discussion, *Gini* is printed as *Gi*.

The original article has been corrected.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-021-00380-6>.

✉ Maria Sassi
maria.sassi@unipv.it

¹ Department of Economics and Management, University of Pavia, Via S. Felice 5, 27100 Pavia, Italy

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